

A Study to Find Out the Efficacy of Combination Method and Comparative Study of Nerve Flossing Technique with and without TENS, in Pain and Disability in Cervical Radiculopathy Patients

Chirag Chabhadiya¹, Deepak Lohar², Jafar Khan³

¹Department of Physiotherapy, Pacific College of Physiotherapy, Udaipur

²Associate Professor of Neurological and Psychosomatic Disorder Department of Physiotherapy Pacific College of Physiotherapy, Udaipur, Rajasthan

³Dean and HOD Pacific College of Physiotherapy, Pacific Medical University, Udaipur, Rajasthan

Received: 25-05-2024 / Revised: 23-06-2024 / Accepted: 26-07-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Chirag Chabhadiya

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Neurodynamic techniques play a significant role in the restoration of neural tissue's ability to stretch and tension, as well as in the stimulation of the reconstruction of normal physiological function of nerve cells. A study is carried out to find the effectiveness of the individual and combination of Nerve Flossing Technique (NFT) and Trans Cutaneous Electrical Nerve Stimulation (TENS) on pain and disability in cervical radiculopathy patients. This study was experimental study, where 60 subjects with chronic cervical radiculopathy with age group 30-55 years were selected by inclusion and exclusion criteria. Subjects who were willing to participate in the study were requested to fill the consent form. Group-A which received TENS and isometric neck exercise, Group-B, received nerve flossing technique and isometric neck exercise and Group C received TENS, NFT and isometric neck exercise. Neck disability index and VAS were taken before the intervention and after the intervention. Data were analysed by SPSS 21.0 software applying, paired t test for within group comparison of NDI and Wilcoxon signed-rank test was used for the VAS & ANOVA and POST HOC test was used for the between group analysis of neck disability index and VAS. The result showed that NFT, TENS & conventional exercise protocol is effective in reduction of score of NDI & VAS after the intervention. This study concluded that Nerve flossing technique Along with TENS and conventional exercise protocol showed more beneficial effect on pain and radiating symptoms in the patients with Cervical radiculopathy with comparison to conventional and only Nerve flossing technique group. Hence NFT can be incorporated in home program with conventional physiotherapy for betterment of patient.

Keywords: Cervical Radiculopathy, Nerve Flossing Technique (NFT), Trans Cutaneous Electrical Nerve Stimulation (TENS).

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Cervical radiculopathy is a condition characterized by the compression and inflammation of the cervical nerve root or roots near the cervical neural foramen. Cervical radiculopathy is a prevalent clinical condition that restricts function, categorized as a nerve root disorder primarily caused by compression or inflammation due to a space-occupying lesion like a herniated disc, cervical osteophyte, spondylitis spur, or hypertrophy of the ligamentum flavum.

This can lead to impingement or inflammation of the nerve root, resulting in various disabilities affecting physical, psychological, and occupational aspects. [1,2] Among the different levels of root compression, the most commonly affected is the C7 root, with reported percentages ranging from 46.3%

to 69%. This is followed by compression of the C6 root (17.6-19%), while compression of the C5 (2-6.6%) and C8 (6.2-10%) roots is less common. [1] The management of cervical radiculopathy relies on a comprehensive grasp of its progression over time, clinical assessment, diagnostic examinations, and available treatment modalities for this condition.

Diagnostic imaging techniques such as radiographs, CT scans, magnetic resonance imaging, myelography discography, etc., along with electrophysiological tests like nerve conduction velocity studies and electromyography, are frequently employed to validate a diagnosis of Cervical Radiculopathy. Additionally, a range of special tests including Spurling's test, TENS test,

upper limb tension test, cervical distraction test, cervical compression test, provocation test, etc., are utilized for clinical diagnosis. [3]

Transcutaneous electrical nerve stimulation:

Transcutaneous electrical nerve stimulation, developed for the management of chronic pain syndromes, transcutaneous electrical nerve stimulation may prove to be even more beneficial in the treatment of acute pain. TENS is especially appropriate for managing neurogenic pain, such as that stemming from peripheral nerve damage, radiculopathies, and similar conditions.

There is experimental evidence to suggest that the analgesic effect of TENS may be modulated by the endogenous opiate system through the release of endorphinergic substances. The vast majority of patients prefer frequencies between 40 and 70 Hz with pulse widths of 100-150 μ s. Leo et al recently compared the effects of four treatment variables on the pain reduction produced by TENS. Although pain was reduced significantly, they found that pulse width, frequency, amplitude, and therapist attributed little to treatment effect, and that subthreshold stimulation proved more effective than stimulation to tolerance. [4]

Nerve Flossing Technique:

Neural mobilization techniques encompass both passive and active movements aimed at re-establishing the nervous system's capacity to withstand the typical pressures and tensions experienced during every day and athletic pursuits. There are two types of neural mobilization: Neurodynamic Tensioners and Neurodynamic Sliders.

Nerve flossing, a form of neural mobilization, represents an active non-invasive therapeutic technique or a conservative approach for addressing neural tissue disorders that offers advantages in terms of efficacy, safety, and cost efficiency, leading to expedited symptom relief. It mobilizes the nerve within the tissues in a bidirectional manner, involving both proximal and distal ends, to maximize the mobilization of each joint and body part that the nerve intersects. This process can be compared to the action of stretching a cord from one end while the other end is loose, and then reversing the direction. [5]

Natural resolution of symptoms and good outcomes are expected in majority of patients, yet there are several studies stating patient with Cervical radiculopathy have more persistent and severe type of pain, a less favourable outcome, long term

disability, withdrawal from work and consumption of more health resources than CRP patients. Thus, there is an overall negative effect on society as the prevalence of radiculopathy is high in working population which leads to more consumption of human resource. So, it becomes important to find therapy which is cost effective reduces pain and disability and make early resume to work possible. So, the need of the study is to compare the effectiveness of TENS, NFT and their combination on Neck Disability Index (NDI) and Visual Analog Scale (VAS) in cervical radiculopathy patients and find the best method for clinical use. This used null hypothesis as well as experimental hypothesis.

In null hypothesis the efficacy of combining nerve flossing technique with and without TENS does not show a significant difference in addressing pain and disability in patients with cervical radiculopathy. In experimental hypothesis the effectiveness of combining nerve flossing technique with transcutaneous electrical nerve stimulation (TENS) in managing pain and disability among patients with cervical radiculopathy shows a notable variation compared to using nerve flossing technique alone

Methodology

To perform this study, study setting at Pacific medical college & hospital, Udaipur is chosen. An interventional study was done where the data was collected from physiotherapy centres in and near study setting areas. The patients suffering from cervical radiculopathy were considered. Convenient Sampling-group allocation by simple random sampling was done where total 60 patients were divided in group A, B and C (each group of 20 patients).

The people with age 30-55 years, both male and female, subjects having radiating symptoms from at least two months (chronic) and the Subjects having median nerve involvement i.e. having positive ULTT for median nerve were involved for the study.

The patients with traumatic cases of upper limb and cervical spine, had undergone any recent surgeries in the neck, hypermobility, having cardiogenic left side upper limb pain, Malignancy for cervical spine, Vertebrobasilar syndrome, TOS, CTS, Etc were excluded from the study. The study continued for 12 weeks. Treatment Table, Pillow, TENS Device, Gel, Electrodes, Pen, Paper, Consent Form (ANNEXURE 1), Assessment form (ANNEXURE 2), Neck Disability Index (ANNEXURE 3) were the materials used for the study.

Figure 1: Material to be used

Method:

- Sixty patients diagnosed with cervical radiculopathy by either an orthopedic or neurologist was chosen to participate in the study based on specific selection criteria.
- Special tests for cervical radiculopathy were performed on each and every participant to confirm the diagnosis. After proper explanation about the purpose and procedure of the study patients who were found suitable and willing to participate in the study were requested to sign consent forms.
- The selection of patients was done by convenient sampling and division of the participants into three groups done by random sampling method. Total 60 patients were divided into three groups. Group-A had 20 patients, Group-B had 20 patients and Group-C had 20 patients. This was a single blinded study as the participants were unaware about the group distribution. All the patients were assessed according to assessment format of cervical radiculopathy. The data measured were recorded in the data collection form.
- The Neck Disability Index (NDI) and Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) were assessed prior to and following the treatment within each of the study groups. Pre-participation evaluation form consisted of assessment chart which included age, sex, chief complains, duration of symptoms, etc.

Clinical Intervention:

- 60 patients were randomly divided equally into three groups by 20 patients in each group were taken and given treatment for 5 days in one week.

Group A

- In Group A Transcutaneous Electrical Nerve Stimulation (TENS) and Conventional therapy was given in cervical radiculopathy patients.
- Placement: Patient was in sitting position, hand was supported on pillow. 1 electrode was placed at lateral to the C5-C7 level of cervical spine and 1 electrode was placed at the end of dermatomal level 20 (FIG 2).
- Parameters: Low TENS was used for the cervical radiculopathy patients. Low frequency 40 to 70 Hz and Wide pulse width: 10-50 microseconds, intensity was gradually increased to patient's tolerance, time duration was 20 minutes.

Following the administration of TENS neck isometric exercises to the individual, a regimen consisting of 10 repetitions per day with a 10-second hold time against near-maximal resistance was implemented.

This treatment protocol was carried out over the course of 5 days within a week (FIG 3 a, b, c and d).

Figure 2: TENS placement for CR

Figure: 3 (a)

Figure: 3 (b)

Figure: 3 (c)

Figures: 3 (d)

Figure 3: Isometric neck exercise for cervical radiculopathy

Group B

- In Group-B all patients were given nerve flossing in sitting position.
- The technique of nerve flossing for the Median Nerve, as described by David Butler, was administered to all participants.
- The upper limb of the patient was moved through a series of motions similar to those used during testing, with the patient in a seated position. This flossing technique mimicked the positions used in median nerve tests, maximizing tension on the nerve and promoting movement.
- The technique involved depressing the shoulder gently, abducting the shoulder from 10-110°, extending the elbow joint, and extending the wrist joint. The sequence included depressing the shoulder, abducting the shoulder from 10-110°, extending the elbow joint, and bringing the wrist joint to a neutral position, all while maintaining a neutral head position.
- The wrist was then extended while the head was in a same-side side-flexion, followed by wrist flexion and opposite-side head flexion. (FIG 4 a and b).
- Flossing technique was given for 2 sets of 6 repetitions.
- This was followed by isometric neck exercises. (A set of 10 repetitions per day with hold time 10 second against near-maximal resistance) (FIG 3 a, b, c and d).
- The treatment was given for 5 days a week.

Figure: 4 (a) NFT starting position

Figure: 4 (b) NFT ending position

Group C

- In Group-C all patients were given the TENS (FIG 2), NFT (FIG 4) and NECK ISOMETRIC EXERCISE (FIG 3).

Results

In this study, total 60 patients were included out of which in group A 50% were male and 50% were female, group B 35% were male and 65% were female and group C were 65% were male and 35% were female.

Three groups were almost similar in terms of age (Group A: mean age 42.2±5.41 years; Group B: mean age 41.75 ± 5.27 years; and Group C: mean age 43.2 ± 6.17 year.) The results were interpreted by:

Statistical software: The Whole statistical analysis was done by using SPSS 21.0 version for windows software. Mean and standard deviation were calculated as measure of central tendency and measure of dispersion respectively.

Statistical Test: Shapiro-wilk test was used to find whether the data was normally distributed or not.

Analysis of pre and post intervention in group A, group B and group C were done by using paired t-test for NDI while analysis of VAS was done by using Wilcoxon Sign Rank Test. Between group comparative analysis of all the 3 groups for NDI and VAS was done by using one way ANOVA test. Post hoc Scheffe’s test was used to find best among three groups in terms of NDI and VAS. Level of significance kept at 0.05 level.

Table 1: Age wise distribution of patients in both the groups

Age	Group A	Group B	Group C
35-40	8	10	9
41-45	5	5	6
46-50	6	3	2
51-55	1	2	3
Total	20	20	20

Figure 5.1

Figure 5.2

Figure 5.3

Figure 5: Graph 5.1, 5.2 and 5.3 Age distribution in years Group A, B AND C

Interpretation: The Above Table and Graphs Shows the Number of Patients and Percentage Distribution in Group A, Group B and Group C.

Table 2: Mean age and standard deviation in all the groups

Age (Years)	Group A	Group B	Group C
MEAN	43.2	41.75	43.2
SD	5.41	5.27	6.17

Figure 6: Mean age and standard deviation in all the groups

Interpretation: The above Table and graft show of age distribution of the 60 patients equally into group A, group B and group C.

Table 3: Gender distribution of patients in both the groups

Gender	Group A	Group B	Group C
Male	10 (50%)	7 (35%)	13 (65%)
Female	10 (50%)	13 (65%)	7 (35%)
Total	20	20	20

Figure 7.1

Figure 7.2

Figure 7.3

Figure 7.1, 7.2, 7.3: Gender distribution of patients in group A, B and C

Interpretation: The above table 5.3 and graph 5.5, 5.6 and 5.7 shows the number of male and female populations participating in the study.

Table 4: Within Group Comparison of Pre and Post NDI Group A, B and C at 5 Days (N=20)

Group	Outcome Measure	Mean ± SD	T Value	P Value	Result
A	NDI	Pre	14.58	0.000	Significant
		Post			
B	NDI	Pre	14.28	0.000	Significant
		Post			
C	NDI	Pre	18.36	0.000	Significant
		Post			

Interpretation: Table 4 shows results of T-test: Values obtained for NDI is in group. A t = 14.58 Group B t = 14.28 and Group C t = 18.36. it concluded that there is highly significant difference in pre and post values of NDI in group A B AND C.

Figure 8: Within group comparison of NDI (mean) group A, B AND C

Figure 9: Within group comparison of NDI (SD) group A, B AND C

Interpretation: The above Figure 8, 9 shows mean and SD for NDI pre and post intervention and obtain value for group A t-14.58 group B t-14.28 and group C t-18.36, it concluded that there is highly significant difference in pre and post values of NDI in group A B AND C.

Table 5: Within group comparison of pre and post VAS group A, B and C at 5 days (N=20)

Group	Outcome Measure	Mean±SD	Z Value	P Value	Result
A	VAS	Pre	-3.98	0.000	Significant
		Post			
B	VAS	Pre	-4.005	0.000	Significant
		Post			
C	VAS	Pre	-4.041	0.000	Significant
		Post			

Interpretation: Table 5 shows the result of Wilcoxon signed rank test: values obtained for VAS in group A Z=-3.98, group B Z= -4.005 and group C Z = -4.041, it is concluded that there is significant difference in pre and post values of VAS in group A and group B and group C.

Figure 10: Within group comparison of VAS (mean) group A, B AND C

Figure 11: Within group comparison of VAS (SD) group A, B AND C

Interpretation: The figure 10,11 shows mean and SD for VAS pre and post intervention and obtain value for group A Z=-3.98 group C Z=-4.005 and group C Z=-4.041. it concluded that there is highly significant difference in pre and post values of VAS in group A B AND C.

Table 6: Between group analysis for difference of NDI and VAS after the 5 days of intervention.

Out Come	Mean Difference ± SD			F Ratio	P Value	Result
	A	B	C			
NDI	12.4 ± 3.80	11.25 ± 3.52	13.60 ± 2.74	2.409	0.099	Not

						significant
VAS	2.85 ± 0.91	2.75 ± 0.91	3.55 ± 0.51	6.145	0.004	Significant

Interpretation: Table 6 shows the result of one-way anova for between group comparative analysis: value obtain for NDI f ratio = 2.409 and vas f ratio = 6.145. Those there is significant difference in value of between 3 group comparison of NDI and VAS after 5 days of intervention.

Figure 12: Between group analysis for difference of NDI and VAS

Interpretation: Figure 12 shows the result of one-way anova for between group comparative analysis: value obtain for NDI f ratio = 2.409 and vas f ratio = 6.145. Thus, there is significant difference in value of between 3 group comparison of NDI and VAS after 5 days of intervention.

Table 7, 8: Between group comparison to find best among three in terms of NDI and VAS after 5 days of interpretation (Post HOC TEST):

Out Come Measure	Group	Group			Interpretation
		A	B	C	
NDI	A	–	0.534	0.505	A-B = Not Significant
					A-C = Not Significant
	B	0.534	–	0.081	B-A = Not Significant
					B-C = Not Significant
	C	0.505	0.081	–	C-A = Not Significant
					C-B = Not Significant

Out Come Measure	Group	Group			Interpretation
		A	B	C	
VAS	A	–	0.915	0.018	A-B = Not Significant
					A-C = Significant
	B	0.915	–	0.006	B-A = Not Significant
					B-C = Significant
	C	0.018	0.006	–	C-A = Significant
					C-B = Significant

Interpretation:

Table 7 shows the result of post hoc test: NDI there is no significant difference between group A, B and C. Table 8 shows VAS and indicates significant difference in group B and C but no significant difference seen in group A.

Discussion & Conclusion

This study was experimental study, where 60 subjects with chronic cervical radiculopathy with

age group 30-55 years were selected by inclusion and exclusion criteria. Subjects who were willing to participate in the study were requested to fill the consent form.

Group-A which received TENA and isometric neck exercise, Group-B, received nerve flossing technique and isometric neck exercise and Group C received TENS, NFT and isometric neck exercise. Neck disability index and VAS were taken before the intervention and after the intervention. Data

were analysed by SPSS 21.0 software applying, paired t test for within group comparison of NDI and Wilcoxon signed-rank test was used for the VAS & ANOVA and POST HOC test was used for the between group analysis of neck disability index and VAS. The result showed that NFT, TENS & conventional exercise protocol is effective in reduction of score of NDI & VAS after the intervention. The results of the present study show significant effects in pre and post evaluation with VAS and NDI at the end of intervention, and in between group comparison shows that NDI accepted null hypothesis and VAS accepted experimental hypothesis. Isometric exercises increase intramuscular coordination by enhancing motor unit activation, synchronization and firing rate within a given muscle. A static contraction generates higher level of tension than concentric contraction. This will lead to increase in muscle strength and improve mobility. [6]

Hence, Isometric exercises might have helped in increasing muscle strength and mobility along with other intervention in all the groups in the study. Isometric exercise is commonly used to increase the muscles performance although no joint movement occurs it is considered functional because it provides a strength base for dynamic exercises and because many postural muscles work primarily in an isometric fashion. [9] The current investigation involved the execution of isometric neck exercises by the subjects in both cohorts over a period of 5 consecutive days. While the participants experienced a decrease in pain and disability, it is not possible to solely attribute these outcomes to the isometric neck exercises due to the brief duration of the exercise regimen. [8]

The results of the current investigation align with Anikwe et al: who researched the influence of NFT on acute sciatica and hip ROM. Group A received NFT along with conventional treatment (Cryotherapy, TENS, soft tissue manipulation and Prone SLR) and Group B was control group receiving only conventional treatment for 15 days. The study findings indicated that both cohorts exhibited significance, with Group A demonstrating a higher level of significance. [10] Hence, it was concluded, as NFT along with TENS

and conventional exercise protocol is more beneficial in reducing pain and radiating symptoms in comparison with NFT and TENS alone, NFT can be incorporated in home program with conventional physiotherapy for betterment of patient.

References

1. Wainner RS, Gill H. Diagnosis and nonoperative management of cervical radiculopathy. *J. Orthop Sports Phys Ther.* 2000; 30:728-744.
2. Cleland JA, Whitman JM, Fritz JM, Palmer JA. Manual physical therapy, cervical traction, and strengthening exercises in patients with cervical radiculopathy: a case series. *J Orthop Sports Phys Ther.* 2005; 35(12):802-11.
3. David J. Magee, *Orthopaedic Physical Assessment*, Elsevier Health Sciences (USA), 4th ed.; 2006; Ch: 3, pg. 145-149.
4. Ronald Melzack, Phyllis Vertere and Lois Finch: *Transcutaneous Electric Nerve Stimulation for Low Back Pain.* *Phy Ther.* 1983; 63:489-493.
5. Pallipamula K, Singaravelan RM. Effects of nerve flossing technique on sciatica due to extruded disc: a case report. *J Phys Ther.* 2013; 8:5-11.
6. Kitai TA, Sale DG. Specificity of joint angle in isometric training. *European journal of applied physiology and occupational physiology.* 1989 Jan 1; 58(7):744- 8.
7. Phillips N. *Advanced Soft Tissue Techniques. Muscle Energy Techniques*, Leon Chaitow. Churchill Livingstone, 2001; 2nd ed. ISBN 0 443 06496 2.
8. Jari Ylinen MD. et al. neck muscles training in treatment of chronic neck pain in women. - a randomized controlled trial. *Journal of American medical association.* 2003, 289:19.
9. Kishner C. Colby LA. *Therapeutic exercises. Foundation and techniques*, FA Davis company, Philadelphia, 5th ed, 2007
10. Anikwe EE, Tella BA, Aiyegbusi AI, Chukwu SC. Influence of Nerve Flossing Technique on acute sciatica and hip range of motion. *International Journal of Medicine and Biomedical Research.* 2015; 4(2):91-9.